

BIAXIAL TESTING OF 3D-C/C COMPOSITE MATERIALS BY A SPECIAL FRAME SYSTEM ON UNIVERSAL TESTER

He Guanhu, Fu Hongyu, Wang Heng,
Dong Shuqing, Zhang Zihua, Zhou Benlian
Institute of Metal Research, Academia Sinica
International Centre for Materials Physics, Academia Sinica
Shenyang 110015, China

ABSTRACT

A special frame-type mechanism has been built up for biaxial strength testing of 3D-C/C composite materials with an uniaxial longitudinal loading on universal tester. Cruciform specimen with reduced thickness at gauge area both for room and high temperature experiments has been designed. Several reliability experiments, such as loading ratio check, two-plane strain measurements, high speed photos of fracture procedure and photoelastic test show the validity of biaxial testing. The biaxial tension testing at high temperatures ($\sim 1000^{\circ}\text{C}$) has also been realized by self-electrical heating of composites. We give strength estimation and results of some 3D-C/C composite materials in this paper.

Key Words: Biaxial testing, Frame-type mechanism, 3D-C/C composite materials

1. INTRODUCTION

For anisotropic 3D-C/C composite materials, the quadratic polynomial form^[1] would be useful as the failure criteria and the coupling coefficient F_{12} should be determined. An optimization process for determining F_{12} has been proposed by uniaxial tension and compression off-axis tests for laminate composites^[2]. We think that the best way of determining F_{12} would be the direct method, i.e. using biaxial testing to get biaxial strength. The cruciform plate specimen of biaxial testing is available for 3D-C/C composite material because of its effective remains of fibres. Considering the high cost by horizontal four hydraulic actuators test machine^[3] and the complex of system control by adding transverse hydraulic system in universal tester^[4], we developed a simple frame mechanism on the universal tester to exert the biaxial tension for 3D-C/C composite materials of uniaxial strength about 200MPa several years ago^[5,6].

Recently, some important improvements, including 1:2 tension-tension, 1:1 tension-compression, 1:1 compression-compression and 1:1 tension-tension at high temperatures ($\sim 1000^{\circ}\text{C}$) by self-electrical heating of specimen, have been fulfilled in our institute. The reliability of mechanism, specimen design and fracture procedure, strength estimation etc., have been discussed.

2. PRINCIPLE AND EQUIPMENT

2.1 Mechanical Analysis of Mechanism

If an uniaxial load P given by 500KN universal hydraulic machine applies to the frame-guide-joint mechanism (Figure 1), from connectors 1, joints 2 and bearings 6, the load P will act on the frame

3 and specimen 4, and the transducers will display the test load. Figure 2 shows the mechanical analysis for popular condition of mechanism. Suppose three points E,C,O, align in the load axis and joints AA' and BB' are parallel to this axis, respectively, one can get the geometry relations and force equilibrium relations:

$$AC=S\sin\alpha, \quad BC=S\cos\alpha \quad (1)$$

$$P_1 \cdot AC=P_2 \cdot BC, \quad P_1+P_2=P \quad (2)$$

$$R_1=P_1 \cos\alpha, \quad R_2=P_2 \sin\alpha \quad (3)$$

where S is the distance between the centre of bearings and the centre of the frame; α , the angle between load axis and one of the specimen axes; R_1 and R_2 , the action loads on the specimen, which will be perpendicular each other. Suppose

$$n=\frac{R_1}{R_2} \quad (4)$$

where, n is the tension ratio of two loads applied to specimen. So, we can get the following equations:

$$\operatorname{tg}\alpha=\left(\frac{1}{n}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

$$R_1=\frac{\cos^2\alpha}{\cos\alpha+\sin\alpha}P=\frac{n}{(1+n^{1/2})(1+n)^{1/2}}P \quad (6)$$

$$Q=\frac{\cos\alpha \sin\alpha}{\cos\alpha+\sin\alpha}P=\frac{n^{1/2}}{(1+n^{1/2})(1+n)^{1/2}}P \quad (7)$$

where Q is the force applied to frame. Therefore, if n and S are the definition respectively, we can get the full geometry and mechanical relation of mechanism shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Geometry relation and mechanical relation of mechanism

n	α	AC	BC	R_1	R_2	Q	η	ΔL
1	45.00°	0.707S	0.707S	0.354P	0.354P	0.354P	0.708	0
2	35.26°	0.577S	0.817S	0.478P	0.239P	0.338P	0.717	0.239S
3	30.00°	0.500S	0.866S	0.549P	0.183P	0.317P	0.732	0.366S

$$\eta=(R_1+R_2)/P, \quad \Delta L=BB'-AA'$$

2.2. Biaxial Testing Equipment at Room Temperature

According to the data given in Table 1 and the basic structure in Figure 1, and referring to the strength of 3D-C/C composite materials, we designed and manufactured the mechanism with

axial symmetry in three dimensions. The specimen grips between specimen and transducers have the shape of semi-ball hinge for self-alignment in loading axis. Figure 3 shows the basic structure of biaxial tension equipment with the tension ratio 1:2. Adding some auxiliary parts, we can change the mode from tension-tension to tension-compression or compression-compression on the same system as tension equipment. Figure 4 shows the compression-compression structures. Careful adjustment of system symmetry before formal experiments is an important step to get exact biaxial stress state.

2.3. Biaxial Tension Equipment at High Temperatures

Suitable electrical resistivity and good thermal conductivity of 3D-C/C composite materials makes the self-electrical heating method for high temperatures possible. Besides the biaxial tension equipment at room temperature, there are three auxiliary systems, i.e. the electrical heating system, the water cooling system and the anti-oxidation system in high temperature experiments. Figure 5 expresses its schematic diagram and Figure 6 shows the system. Special designed water cooled transducer to avoid test load data shift and the electrodes holder to reduce extra force onto specimen as small as possible were the important efforts for experiment success.

2.4. Specimen Design and Preparation

We designed cruciform specimen with electrical connection both for room and high temperature biaxial testing. Figure 7 shows the basic shape of specimen. The thickness of gauge area, t , ($t=2\sim 3\text{mm}$) is different for different kind of composites or for different principal direction of material. The ratio of T/t is about $1.5\sim 2.0$ and the aim of the reduction of thickness at gauge area is to ensure that the stress in this area is largest than that of other areas. In machining of specimen, the full bundle of fibres must be remain, be parallel with the specimen plane and be distributed uniformly along the specimen thickness. Critical examination for every machining step and final examination by special tools were of necessity to obtain qualified specimen.

3. EVALUATION OF EXPERIMENTS RELIABILITY

The biaxial testing must satisfy following conditions: the stress in gauge area is basically uniform; maximum stress, or first failure, must appear in the gauge area and the calculation of strength should be simple; biaxial loading must be exerted along the axes synchronously.

3.1. Biaxial Testing of Cast Aluminium Alloy

Firstly, the reliability of mechanism should be checked using isotropic materials. We chose one kind of cast aluminium alloy material as a quasi-isotropic sample. Three specimens with the shape like Figure 7 were measured for tension-tension(T-T), tension-compression (T-C) and compression-compression(C-C) in the loading (P) range of 40KN, 30KN and 44KN, which would be similar to those used for 3D-C/C composites, respectively. Triangular strain sheets stick on the corresponding location of two planes of specimen gauge area. The results have been given in Table 2. The relative loading deviation of same axis of specimen is less than 3% and the relative strain deviation between the corresponding location of two planes of gauge area and specimen central plane is mostly less than 15%. These results would be acceptable for engineering application. The largest deformation of frame near the guide area is about 10 micro-strains and its effect on the deviation between loading axis and specimen axis would be negligible.

3.2 High Speed Photos of Fracture Procedures

In our experiments, the testing load on specimen may not be released after fracture at once and the fracture section will be of transversality of specimen. So it is essential to confirm if the fracture originates from gauge area first. We adapted high speed photo technique to search the crack origination. Figure 8 is the results of high speed photos with 3000-4000 size per second for 1:2 tension-tension of 3D-C/C composites. The stretching procedure of occurring crack in gauge area could be seen clearly from these photos.

Table 2 Results of biaxial testing for cast aluminium alloy

testing mode		T-T 1:1				T-C 1:1				C-C 1:1			
general loading P(KN)		40				30				44			
R(KN)		1	13.15	3	13.35	1	-10.28	3	-10.33	1	-15.01	3	-14.59
		2	13.06	4	13.36	2	10.11	4	10.24	2	-15.24	4	-14.98
δ(%)	13	1.5				0.4				2.1			
	24	2.2				1.4				2.7			
ε(%)		1	980	4	844	1	-2213	4	-2415	1	-876	4	-1171
		2	1202	5	979	2	1377	5	978	2	-818	5	-1122
		3	973	6	774	3	1477	6	1146	3	-1214	6	-1345
E(%)	14	7.5				4.4				14.5			
	25	10.2				12.6				15.5			
	36	11.4				17.3				5.1			
$\delta_{ij} = \frac{R_i - R_j}{(R_i + R_j)/2} \quad i,j=1,3; 2,4$ $E_{ij} = \frac{\epsilon_i - \epsilon_j}{\epsilon_i + \epsilon_j}, \quad i,j=1,4; 2,5; 3,6$													

Table 3 Typical biaxial testing results of 3D-C/C composites

No	Composites	T/t	mode	R ₁ (KN)	R ₂ (KN)	R ₃ (KN)	R ₄ (KN)	σ ₆ MPa	δ ₁₃	δ ₂₄	n'	note
1	A-3D-C/C	1.4	T-T 1:2	12.50	6.41	12.70	6.59	190	1.6	2.7	1.98	room temp.
2	B-3D-C/C	2.0	C-C 1:1	9.44	9.37	9.70	9.25	117	2.7	1.3	1.05	room temp.
3	C-3D-C/C	1.72	T-C 1:1	6.16	6.15	6.11	6.12	77	0.8	0.6	1.01	room temp.
4	D-3D-C/C	1.68	T-T 1:2	14.86	7.32	14.99	7.46	161	0.9	1.9	2.05	room temp.
5	D-3D-C/C	1.98	T-T 1:1	15.88	16.00	16.07	16.35	182	1.2	2.1	1.03	994°C

3.3 Uniformity of Stress in Gauge Area and Estimation of Strength

The finite element stress analysis has been carried out in another work^[7] and the results show that the stress in gauge area would be basically uniform. Furthermore, the penetrating photoelastic measurements for epoxy resin specimen under biaxial testing load on mechanism have been exerted. As a sample, Figure 9 is the stress equal-differential pattern for compress-compress at different testing load (a)0.6KN, (b)1.45KN and (c)2.16KN. It can be seen from Figure 9 that in gauge area the stripe display its uniform stress basically because no colour stripes existed.

We hope to find a simple formula to estimate the strength of 3D-C/C composites. The special shape of specimen and complex stress distribution in the specimen, however, make the problem rather difficult. The finite element analysis proposes a calculation of strength as^[7]

$$\sigma = K \frac{R_1}{b.t} \quad (8)$$

Where $K (<1)$ is a revision constant for different T/t and different materials, R_1 , the axis loading of specimen, b , the width of specimen wedge and t , the thickness of gauge area of specimen.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Several kinds of 3D-C/C composites has been tested for biaxial testing at room temperature, including tension-tension (T-T), tension-compression (T-C), compression-compression (C-C) and for biaxial tension at high temperatures. Table 3 gives the results of some typical experiments of four kinds of 3D-C/C composites. Figure 10 shows the fracture shape of specimens. The relative loading deviation of same axis of specimen, δ_{13} and δ_{24} , is less than 3% for all experiments and the deviation between biaxial testing ratio n' and ratio n , is mostly less than 3%.

In order to check the reliability of strength estimation Equation (8), we measured the uniaxial strength by uniaxial testing specimens and compared these data with the strength get from uniaxial testing using biaxial specimens. The results presented the acceptability of strength estimation.

4.2 Discussion

We will discuss some error factors on experiments. For this special frame-type system, the biaxial testing depends on the exact symmetry of mechanism. Careful preparation of specimen and precise adjustment of mechanism can ensure the validity of biaxial loading for isotropic specimens. We don't think it impossible that the biaxial testing can be satisfied for anisotropic specimens. Fortunately, the strain measurement of 3D-C/C composites showed that its maximum fracture strains would be in the range of 3000 micro-strains. So, the asymmetry of mechanism due to the different strains in different directions would be so small, say less than 1%, that this effect can be negligible for biaxial testing of 3D-C/C composites.

Another two error factors are self-weight of mechanism for room temperature tests and extra force of electrodes on specimen for high temperature tests. We put the multi-layer rubber between the bearings and frame and the thickness of upper side rubber is bigger than that of lower side. This arrangement makes the test load of specimen in same axis at upper and lower parts equal and only the load applied to frame guide and rubbers (in frame diagonal), because of the self-weight of frame, is different for upper and lower parts.

The electrodes connect on the specimen by stainless steel screw bolts and nuts for high temperature experiments. Before screwing them, we hold the electrodes on the guide cylinder of test machine and make the electrodes equilibrium. So, only a little part of loads (less than kilograms) acting on the specimen and the adding load could not effect the free-deformation of specimen during experiments. The fracture shape (Figure 10) expresses the validity of high temperature biaxial tension.

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. A special frame-type biaxial testing equipment has been developed. The biaxial testing can be exerted on universal tester by this special system. The experiments on quasi-isotropic aluminium alloy specimen, high speed photo of fracture procedure of 3D-C/C composites and photoelastic experiments on epoxy resin specimen present the reliability of biaxial testing.

2. For anisotropic 3D-C/C composite materials, the small fracture strains could not effect the symmetry of mechanism and the biaxial testing of 3D-C/C composites can be exerted by using

this frame-type mechanism. The biaxial strength estimation of 3D-C/C composites is acceptable.

3. The self-electrical heating method of 3D-C/C composites to carry out the high temperature ($\sim 1000^{\circ}\text{C}$) biaxial tension has been adapted by this frame-type system with auxiliary electrical heating system, water cooling system and anti-oxidation system. The results, including two direction tension ratio, deviation of test load in same axis and fracture shape of specimen, show that this method can be used to the engineering application.

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Figure 1. Schematic diagram of biaxial tension mechanism

Figure 2 Mechanical analysis of biaxial tension mechanism

Figure 3 Biaxial tension structure with $n=2$

Figure 4 Biaxial compression structure with $n=1$

Figure 5 Schematic diagram of high temperature biaxial tension system

- 1 argon vessel 2 pressure meters 3 flow meter
- 4 argon pipes 5 load transducers (4)
- 6 leads for load signals (4) 7 shells (two half)
- 8 specimen 9 water coolings 10 electrodes
- 11 leads for heating 12 current meter
- 13 pre-adjuster 14 strain detector 15 printer
- 16 holder 17 transformer
- 18 transformer for voltage adjuster

Figure 6 High temperature biaxial tension system

Figure 7 Specimen design

Figure 8 High speed photo of fracture with biaxial tension $n=2$ (3D-C/C)

Figure 9 Photoelastic pictures of biaxial compression (epoxy resin)

Figure 10 Fracture shape of specimens